

ASPECTS OF MANIFESTATION OF ANXIETY AMONG CADETS IN EXTREME SITUATIONS

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Abstract.

In this article, the emotional-volitional characteristics of 100 military personnel from the Institute of Communication Technologies were studied using the method study of reactive anxiety of Ch.D. Spielberg - Yu.L. Khanin).

Keywords. Emotional-volitional features, cadets, extreme situations.

Acknowledgments and funding. The study was carried out as part of a psychological analysis of the moral and volitional qualities of future officers.

Introduction

Global changes are taking place in the world caused by the variability of the nature of military aggression of the armed forces, the instability of strategic interaction, trends in the formation of new combat means and methods of armed struggle, social and economic changes in society, the intensification of international terrorism and extremism, as well as other dangerous factors.

In this regard, it is extremely important to study the diagnostics of the emotional and volitional characteristics of servicemen in extreme situations.

Resistance to the moral and psychological stress associated with a military conflict, while maintaining a certain opinion and strong will, means maintaining the combat capability of the troops and military formations of the country. Under these conditions, the reduction of psychogenic losses, the speedy restoration of the mental abilities of personnel to continue combat missions within the framework of combat (special) operations, is of particular importance.

After analyzing the psychological and pedagogical literature on this issue, we concluded that the opinions of researchers in the definition of the concept of "emotional-volitional stability" are contradictory. Works in which emotional stability is considered as a characteristic of the emotional sphere of a person, the stability of emotions, emotional stability, and the absence of a tendency to frequent changes of emotions have become widespread (Ayzenck X, Berezin F.B. and others).

Methods and materials

Research methods. Method study of reactive anxiety of Ch.D. Spielberg - Yu.L. Khanin, mathematical and statistical analysis for calculating the results obtained (Student's t-test, K. Pearson's correlation analysis method).

The purpose is to study the problem of psychological aspects of the dynamics of emotional and volitional characteristics of the personnel of the armed forces in extreme and difficult situations. The objectives of the study are to determine the factors of origin and the specifics of the volitional characteristics of military personnel in extreme and difficult situations.

The object of the study are 100 cadets from the Institute of Communication Technologies.

The subject of the research is the study of the dynamics of the volitional characteristics of future officers in extreme and difficult situations. Analysis of the degree of study of volitional characteristics in domestic and foreign psychology.

Results and discussion

In our opinion, attention to the development and formation of the dynamics of volitional characteristics in military personnel will help to analyze the process of formation of their personality. We call a strong-willed person with a certain set of character traits - this is willpower, energy, perseverance, endurance, which we also investigated and reflected in Table 1. The studies were carried out with a certain complication, in particular, measurements were made after shooting and descending from a height.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of the volitional qualities of future officers according to the methodology C.D. Spielberger – Yu.L. Khanina (N=100)

Indicators	Cadets ICT	t-test	Test standard deviation	Correlation Pearson
	Interest rate %			
Low reactive anxiety	98%	0,07960**	0,05616	0,99602
Mean reactive anxiety	2%	0,07960**		0,99963
High reactive anxiety	0%	0,18169**		0,70710

Note: ** with statistically significant changes.

Cadets of military institutes represent a special aggregate subject of social relations. Stress factors of the learning process, namely, overload with training sessions, insufficient consideration of the individual characteristics of cadets in training and education, as well as serious physical, informational and emotional stresses reduce the level of psychophysical culture of cadets.

As a result, it becomes more difficult for cadets to overcome various stressful situations, which can cause a decrease in professional activity, the development of psychosomatic diseases, nervous exhaustion, disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, and the cardiovascular system. Thus, the formation and development of personal, including emotional and volitional, stability of future defenders of the Fatherland is becoming a priority issue, since today practice shows that not all military personnel are psychologically ready to effectively perform their professional duties in mastering modern technologies in complex and extreme conditions (Astapov 2008).

The problem of emotional-volitional stability is one of the most complex and relevant in modern science. Many scientists pay great attention to the issue of the influence of emotional and volitional factors on the success of human activity in various conditions, especially extreme ones. The ability of a person to regulate his mental state in situations of strong

emotional stress, showing his best volitional qualities, is of great pedagogical and psychological significance for regulating all his activities and behavior (Berezin 2000).

For the sake of objectivity, it is necessary to consider the problem of will and the development of volitional qualities of a person from the point of view of pedagogy, based on the study of practical technologies and means of education. This fact determines the priority direction of psychological research in the emotional and volitional sphere of personality (Sabadash 2000).

The results of the study of the listed volitional features are presented in the form of a diagram in Figure 1.

Figure.1 Diagram of the results of determining reactive anxiety among cadets according to the Spielberger-Khanin method.

Cadets of higher educational institutions, being in their youth, go through the stage of growing up and becoming a person in very strict and restrictive conditions (Smirnov & Dolgopolova 2007).

At this age, desires and aspirations develop faster than will and strength of character. Among the features of the cadets, one can single out directness of judgments, acute susceptibility and increased emotionality. This is especially evident in the first year of study, when cadets encounter a new environment and there is a contradiction between the usual forms of behavior and statutory requirements (Gray 1999).

Obviously, the emotional-volitional stability of young men in this situation is very low. The process of restructuring old stereotypes and developing new ones is quite painful and can cause negative mental reactions. At this stage of training, the main task of teachers and course officers will be to assist cadets in developing the skills and abilities of independent work in a military school.

Cadets of the second year of study are characterized by higher emotional and volitional stability, since they already have some experience of studying and serving in a military university. Close-knit military collectives are formed among them, and their actions in fulfilling the military regulations become more confident.

In the third year of study, the basic professional skills and abilities of future officers have already been formed, the worldview becomes meaningful, which allows cadets to strengthen their ideological positions. The emotional and volitional stability of military personnel is

strengthened, since the acquired knowledge develops into convictions and the cadets already have the ability to defend them with arguments.

Graduation cadets become professionally formed personalities: they develop a stable life position and character traits, and their abilities are fully revealed.

Together, these qualities characterize the strong will of a person. A strong will is needed for a warrior to successfully solve, above all, combat missions. The fact is that it is combat efforts that contain various factors that have a negative impact on the will of a person. Danger can cause illness, fear, confusion, as previously mentioned. In order to successfully complete a combat mission, to use equipment and military weapons most effectively, and to control their behavior, a warrior must suppress negative feelings.

Let us consider in more detail the influence of the state of anxiety on the effectiveness of actions when performing tasks. It is important for a soldier to maintain productive intellectual activity in tense situations. At the same time, anxiety makes it difficult to work in situations that require any kind of tension. Anxiety has the strongest impact on performance in stressful situations under the influence of stress factors. Highly anxious in a stressful situation cannot show results corresponding to the level of their claims. Before the start of live firing, the level of anxiety among the majority of military personnel rises, since the impact of the expected danger may exceed the impact of the real danger itself. In the process of completing the task, anxiety is somewhat dulled, and after the task is completed, the level of anxiety rises again. In our experience, there is also a different reaction of non-anxious and highly anxious servicemen to unsatisfactory shooting results. The former more often seek to retake the assessment, while the latter do not make such requests. Moreover, they often have an avoidance reaction. They try to avoid the next shooting under any pretext, which further increases the difference in the estimated indicators between these two categories (Clark & Beck 2019).

A subjectively experienced threat entails an increased concentration of attention on oneself and prevents the individual from concentrating on the task being performed. The subject cannot, for this reason, focus on the object of the threat, and this entails disorientation, inadequate responses to threats and disorganization of activity. Anxiety affects the psychological basis of a person's self-awareness, on which the perception of one's "I" is built. With anxiety-fearful excitement, the disorganization of human behavior caused by anxiety reaches a maximum, and the possibility of purposeful activity is significantly weakened.

The perception of danger by military personnel (an element of danger is a frequently present component in their activities) also depends on their individual indicators of anxiety. Namely: highly anxious tend to exaggerate the degree of danger, while low anxiety, on the contrary, underestimate. Both are "harmful" for military professional activity.

Taking this into account, we assumed that the deployment of military professional activity among highly anxious military personnel will be characterized by inadequate goal-setting, inability to highlight the main thing in their activity, a decrease in the accuracy and automaticity of actions, and a deterioration in the emotional and mental state.

This may result in a decrease in performance. Inadequately calm military personnel due to excessive self-confidence will also make mistakes in the performance of military training activities, ignore security measures, and inattentively prepare for classes. The results of the study of the listed reactive anxiety are presented in the form of a diagram in Table 1.

Not so much the complexity of the task being performed, but the fear and expectation of failure plays the role of a distraction, the influence of which is easier for individuals with a high level of anxiety. With high anxiety, negative events are perceived more painfully. Minor issues, if they require choice and volitional effort, become complex, grow to the level of a problem, and a person has a desire to get away from them. It follows from this that highly anxious servicemen will be oppressed by any activity that requires initiative, and initiative and independence in making decisions are professionally important qualities of future commanders(Misyashchev V.N. 2011).

In the United States, a well-known researcher of anxiety is K. Spielberger. He identifies two concepts, two forms of anxiety - anxiety as a state (ST) and as a property (LT). The division of anxiety into ST and LT has firmly entered into psychological use and has become very convenient not only in theory, but also in diagnostic and experimental practice. In a similar way, he proposes to distinguish between the anxiety and anxiety of the Levites, as already shown above, with the difference that the latter is considered by him as a character trait. ST is congruent to a temporary emotional state caused by the action of factors that contain a real or imagined danger for the individual. LT reflects a fairly stable individual property, which is determined by the subject's tendency to perceive a threat to his own personality and the willingness to respond to this by increasing CT in conditions of even a slight danger or stress. In other words, anxiety as a property describes relatively stable individual differences in an individual's propensity to experience a state of anxiety. Regarding the ratio of the two named forms of anxiety, it is indicated that ST should be considered genetically primary, and LT should be considered secondary. The life experience of a person, fixing the frequency and intensity of the experienced states of anxiety, directly affects the formation of anxiety as a personality trait; LT, on the other hand, determines the features of the functioning of the ST when it is updated and, therefore, acts as the base in such a case (Prihojan 2011).

Increased anxiety arises and is realized as a result of a complex interaction of cognitive, affective and behavioral reactions provoked when a person is exposed to various stresses. Otherwise, anxiety can be caused by many different factors. Among them are such as: the probable inability of the subject to realize significant aspirations in the future; a threat to the prestige of self-esteem in a situation of interpersonal relationships; discrepancy between self-assessments and assessments of others. The brain structures responsible for the manifestation of anxiety are the sections of the upper trunk and the limbic region.

The brain structures responsible for the manifestation of anxiety are the sections of the upper trunk and the limbic region. With pathological excitation of these systems, symptoms of increased excitability, anxiety, high distractibility by any stimuli are noted.

The measurement of anxiety as a personality trait is especially important, since this property largely determines the behavior of the subject. A certain level of anxiety is a natural and obligatory feature of an active active person. Each person has their own optimal or desirable level of anxiety - this is useful anxiety. A person's assessment of his state in this respect is an essential component of self-control and self-education for him. Personal anxiety is understood as a stable individual characteristic that reflects the subject's predisposition to anxiety and implies a tendency to perceive a fairly wide "fan" of situations as threatening, responding to each of them with a specific reaction.

This state occurs as an emotional reaction to a stressful situation and can be different in intensity and dynamism over time. Individuals classified as highly anxious tend to perceive a threat to their self-esteem and life in a wide range of situations and respond with a very pronounced state of anxiety. If a psychological test expresses a high level of personal anxiety in a subject, then this gives grounds to assume the appearance of a state of anxiety in various situations, especially when they relate to assessing their competence and prestige.

Most of the known methods for measuring anxiety allow you to evaluate only personal, or the state of anxiety, or more specific reactions. The only method that allows differentially measuring anxiety both as a personal property and as a state is the method proposed by C. D. Spielberger. In Russian, this scale was adapted by Yu. L. Khanin. Low anxiety signals that the subject needs to increase the sense of responsibility and awareness of the real motives of his own activity. But sometimes very low anxiety is evidence of a person's active displacement of high anxiety in order to show himself in a "better light". It is known that anxiety and anxiety are closely related to stress. Due to this, tests that assess the severity of anxiety can also be successfully used to diagnose the level of stress. At the same time, situational anxiety will characterize the level of stress at the moment, and personal anxiety - vulnerability (or resistance) to the effects of various stressors in general. The assessment of anxiety as a stable personality trait is important in the selection of personnel, the formation of teams taking into account psychological compatibility, especially for work in conditions of increased danger, when responsible, cautious performers are needed, capable of analyzing and generalizing information, avoiding conflict situations.

In Table 1, also from the presented diagram, it can be seen that in 98% of the courses during training sessions, "low reactive anxiety" occurs, in our opinion, this is because they do not yet participate in hostilities.

A person's assessment of his condition in this respect is an essential component of self-control and self-education.

Situational or reactive anxiety as a condition is characterized by subjectively experienced emotions: tension, anxiety, concern, nervousness. The results of determining the reactive anxiety of cadets according to the Spielberger-Khanin method are shown in fig. 1.

It can be seen from the diagram that the cadets have underestimated «median reactive anxiety» and «high reactive anxiety», these indicators need to be corrected. It is possible to correct these indicators for cadets by psychological trainings.

Conclusion.

At the end of the study, the following conclusions were formulated.

Serviceman's anxiety is a private, specific type of anxiety, which is a serviceman's tendency to experience emotional discomfort caused by subjectively exaggerated danger in situations of military service that do not really threaten well-being.

The severity of anxiety largely determines the structured nature of the motives for mastering military professional activity. The higher the anxiety, the less represented the internal motives of military professional activity and the motivation to achieve success. Highly anxious military personnel are dominated by external motives for military activity and the motivation to avoid failure. In the hierarchy of motives, they are dominated by the motives of facilitating the conditions of service, social prestige and benefits. Non-anxious servicemen are dominated by internal motives of military activity and the motivation to achieve success. In

the hierarchy of motives, they are dominated by the motives of mastering a profession, leadership, and acquiring new knowledge.

High anxiety disrupts the implementation of military-professional activities. This is evident when performing difficult tasks. Military-professional actions in highly anxious servicemen are characterized by a violation of accuracy and coordination of movements, inconsistency, and a large number of erroneous movements. In non-anxious servicemen, military-professional actions are relatively well coordinated and are distinguished by the accuracy of movements, the minimum number of errors, and the absence of significant differences in the performance of complex and simple actions.

In the broadest sense, the regulation of anxiety can be carried out in two ways: the prevention of its occurrence and the elimination of conditions that have already arisen. Each of these paths can be carried out either through influences on the human psyche from the outside (for example, the impact of a psychologist on a soldier through the use of psycho-regulatory training, the use of color, music, natural landscape), or through the influence itself (self-hypnosis, self-persuasion, self-orders).

The practical significance of the results of the study makes it possible to correctly orient the emotional and volitional characteristics in the diagnosis of military personnel, their achievement of successful performance of their duties in combat, extreme, difficult situations. Commanders, help their subordinates, distribute tasks in accordance with their capabilities and abilities. Based on these studies, military psychologists have the opportunity to conduct adequate psycho-correction.

The scientific significance of the research results lies in the fact that it enriches military and social psychology with new scientific data. The revealed regularities, psychological mechanisms that contribute to military and social psychology serve to create new scientific research in this area.

Limitations and future research. An empirical study carried out according to the Spielberger-Khanin method in complicated conditions close to combat, it is recommended to additionally conduct an observation method and a survey on real well-being.

Therefore, in the second part of the study (to be published later), the obtained results were compared to determine the impact on the emotional characteristics of military personnel, using the Bass-Darky method to study aggressiveness.

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